
EMBRACE: explications and examples

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Abstract

In the present paper we provide additional details and explanations to the evaluation process performed as part of the research described in the article *EMBRACE: Evaluation and Modifications for Boosting RACE*. This paper is synchronised with the main article in structure and content, and the titles of the sections are kept the same to facilitate the search for corresponding materials.

Here, we also illustrate specific cases of identification of variables and errors with examples mainly taken from the evaluated corpus (test set of RACE-H) – the ordinal numbers of the MCQs as they can be found in the corpus (<https://github.com/dkalpakchi/EMBRACE>) are attached to all such examples and are given in parenthesis. All MCQs taken from the RACE corpus as examples are presented as they are found in the original data, regardless of the grammatical and/or formatting errors they contain. Originally erroneous spelling and/or formatting are sometimes corrected in this paper for ease of reading, with an asterisk (*) to mark the edited word or piece of text. For cases where only one alternative is provided as an example in this paper, this alternative is marked as the correct answer in the original dataset.

1 Terminology

Here we define the main terms we use during the evaluation process which regulate our treatment of the involved dimensions.

- **MCQ unit** refers to the combination of the question¹, the correct answer² to this question, and incorrect, but plausible options called distractors.
- **Alternatives** refer to the the correct answer and distractors together.
- **MCQ** refers to the combination of the text, and an MCQ unit based on this text.
- **MCQ element** refers separately to the text, question, or alternatives, all given for one MCQ.

¹ the same as “stem”, the terms are used interchangeably in this article

² the same as “key”, the terms are used interchangeably in this article

2 Evaluation variables

2.1 Type of information (TOI)

Identification and categorisation of the TOI concept is mainly straightforward, since in many cases it can be derived from the question word (e.g., “*When?*” – *time*; “*How many?*” – *amount* etc.). However, a question word as such is not always a valid predictor of TOI, because of several reasons:

- ***lack of context*** for the requested information (e.g., “*Why did he start writing books?*” might refer both to cause/reason and goal/purpose; “*Where?*” as such represents both place and location);
- ***nature of the question*** sometimes makes it too broad or unspecified (e.g., “*What do we know from the text?*”, “*What is true about X?*”);
- ***a question word is not in the query*** when the latter is formulated as a complete-the-sentence or fill-in-the-gap task (e.g., *The author wanted to tell us the importance of _ by writing this passage.*(3507)³).

For cases when a question word cannot be used as a valid predictor of TOI, the corresponding correct answer is used for a broader context. Thus, for a question like “*Why did Peter start writing a book?*”, potential correct answers and corresponding TOI identification would be as follows (Table 1):

Key	TOI concept (Points)	Explanation
to become famous	goal (3)	refers to a desired outcome
to earn more money	purpose (3)	refers to an intended effect
because he was bored	cause (4)	refers to information that produces a change in state resulting in a new state called an effect
because it was the only way to keep himself busy	reason (4)	refers to information that describes foregoing circumstances or conditions

Table 1: TOI identification, context-dependent

If at least one of the alternatives is needed for a broader context to define TOI, we take into account all given alternatives. This allows (1) to conduct the evaluation in a more precise manner (see Figure 1) and (2) to separate MCQs where all alternatives represent the same TOI concept, from those with at least two alternatives (which might include the correct answer) of distinct TOI concepts, and score the groups differently. For comparison, see Figures 2 and 3.

Note: for cases, when there is the only alternative to differ in terms of TOI concept (regardless of if it is the key or not), the MCQ unit is considered *inconsistent within alternatives* and appears then as the one containing errors (see Figure 4).

³ here and further in the article, numbers in parenthesis refer to ordinal numbers of questions in the RACE corpus taken for evaluation (`num` field in the JSON files), unless other is specified

Question:*(541) Who benefited most from the project?*

Alternatives	TOI concept (Points)
(A) Older pupils.	attribute (2) + group (1)
(B) Pupils who were not confident.	group (1) + attribute (2)
(C) Younger pupils.	attribute (2) + group (1)
(D) Pupils who were confident.	group (1) + attribute (2)
“pupils” to define <i>group</i> as a TOI category makes part of all alternatives and has no impact on evaluation, so is excluded from annotation → TOI = attribute (2)	

Figure 1: TOI: excluded element

Question:*What do we know about Peter, according to the passage?*

Alternatives	TOI concept (Points)
(A) He works as a doctor.	job / group (1)
(B) He works as a policeman.	job / group (1)
(C) He works as a baker.	job / group (1)
(D) He works as an ambulance driver.	job / group (1)
	= job / group (1)

Figure 2: TOI: same concept in all alternatives

Question:*What do we know about Peter, according to the passage?*

Alternatives	TOI concept (Points)
(A) He works as a doctor.	job / group (1)
(B) He examined the child after the accident.	action (2)
(C) It was his son who suffered in the accident.	assertion (4)
(D) He works as an ambulance driver.	job / group (1)
	= indeterminate (5)

Figure 3: TOI: different concepts

Question:

What do we know about Peter, according to the passage?

Alternatives	TOI concept (Points)
(A) He works as a doctor.	job / group (1)
(B) He works as a policeman.	job / group (1)
(C) It was his son who suffered in the accident.	assertion (4)
(D) He works as an ambulance driver.	job / group (1)
	= assertion (3); inconsistency between A

Figure 4: TOI: erroneous MCQ

2.2 Type of match (TOM)

2.2.1 Literal match

- *verbatim correpondence*

- (3139) [T] The Winter Solstice is an important festival at the South Pole.
 [Q] The Winter Solstice is an important festival - .
 [A] at the South Pole

- *contractions* (e.g., *you have set* – *you’ve set*, *did not use* – *didn’t use* etc.);

- *incomplete correspondence between proper names* (skipped names/surnames), if all names differ and no confusion is possible when these are shortened (e.g., *George Bernard Shaw* - *Shaw*, *Amanda Leopold* - *Amanda / Leopold*), etc.);

- *paronymous adjectives with close meaning* (e.g., *historic* - *historical*, *numeric* - *numerical*, etc.);

- *exchanged phrases/clauses* if all are parts of one and the same sentence

- (156) [T] Since the 1950s, most of the stars of pop music have come from Britain and America.
 [Q] Since the 1950s,most of the stars of pop music have come from - .
 [A] America and Britain

- (2251) [T] [...] magical thinking can be a great help, explained Dr. Daniel Wegner
 [...] [Q] Which of the following is true according to the next?
 [A] Dr. Daniel Wegner explained magic thinking can be a great help.

- *a piece of information (a word/phrase/clause) from the text is skipped in a target alternative and is irrelevant for this particular MCQ context*, whereas all other components of the target MCQ element represent a word-by-word match to the text

- (2147) [T] Bram Stoker’s Dracula is powerful, yet old and physically ugly.
 [A] Powerful, old and ugly.

Note: *no piece of information from a question or an alternative can be skipped*, since each of them conveys an additional condition/feature to control and impacts complexity degree

(2811) [T] *He wanted to tell his wife how much he loved her; he felt sorry to have hurt her sometimes.*

[Q] *Richard felt sorry to his wife because ..*

The pronominal reference “he – Richard” requires a reader to relate the given excerpt to the previous paragraph in the text (see scoring differences for this in section 2.6).

2.2.2 Synonymous match (SM)

- a result of **vocabulary replacements**

(2720) [T] *[...] if you dream about being in good health, then change your dream to see yourself working out and eating right day by day.*

[Q] *If you want to keep fit, -*

- a result of **grammar alterations** or **a word family involvement**

(2733) [T] *A home is more than a roof and four walls. It's the cooking, eating, talking, playing and family living that go on inside, which are important as well.*

[A] *cook, talk, and play games*

(2261) [T] *Men are more likely to have much less patience than women. That is why their stress levels are much higher than women when they are sitting still in traffic.*

[A] *Because they are less patient than women.*

- **a combination of vocabulary replacement(s) with grammar alteration(s) or word family involvement**

(2233) [T] *In changing its name from Cal State, Hayward, to Cal State, East Bay, the university hoped to project its expanding role in two mostly suburban counties east of San Francisco.*

[A] *hopes to expand its influence).*

- **numbers written in words/digits and used interchangeably** (e.g., *one hundred pupils - 100 pupils*, etc.).

2.2.3 Low-level text-based inference (LLTI)

- resolving **pronominal references** includes substitutions of a noun phrase with a personal pronoun, linking possessive pronouns (possessive case of nouns) to corresponding proper names or common nouns, inferencing between that previously stated/described and demonstrative, relative, reciprocal, or reflexive pronouns

(2745) [T] *[...] a friend told me that his dad, who played Santa Claus in my area, would be willing to make a visit on Christmas morning to our home with the gifts!*

[Q] *What did the friend's father do that Christmas morning?*

[A] *He acted as Santa Claus to send Christmas gifts.*

- drawing **inferences within several clauses/sentences** in the text (can also be within different parts of a paragraph or different paragraphs; can be a dialogue)

(1607) [T] “Humans have a code of ethics ,” says Marc Bekoff, an animal behavior expert at the University of Colorado. “ If I don’t play in a certain way, you won’t play with me. Some animals have the same code.”

[Q] It can be learned from the passage that - .

[A] some animals also have a code of ethics like human beings.

(1621) [T] I’m a (woman)photographer. I make plenty of money, travel a lot, and meet a lot of people. I enjoy my work, and would hate to stay at home. I would never marry a man who wanted me to give up my work.

[Q] The woman photographer would not marry a man who - .

[A] wants her to stay at home

- inferring **the definition given a term, or the term given a definition** means that an explanation of a thing/phenomenon/phrase mentioned in the text is directly or indirectly requested by the question and can be transformed/paraphrased from or to one word

(1245) [T] After the operation, she adapted quickly.

[A] She accepted the result and tried to get used to it.

(1538) [T] However, mirror-walled skyscrapers raise the temperature of the surrounding air and affect neighboring buildings.

[A] The surrounding air is heated.

- recognising **patterns** relates to the type of inference when a correct answer represents a repetitive action or phenomenon which is inferable from the examples given in the text by rephrasing what is already stated in the text (though not by synonymous substitution(s))

(4) [T] Lying has great value to the evolution of human being. Researchers have long known that the more intelligent the species, the more likely it is to lie. [...]

[Q] The examples of kids lying in the passage show - .

[A] lying is a sign of intelligent development

(12) [T] Although most weddings follow long-held traditions, there’s still room for American individualism. For example, the usual place for a wedding is in a church. But some people get married outdoors in a scenic spot. A few even have the ceremony while skydiving or riding on horseback! The couple may invite hundreds of people or just a few close friends. They choose their own style of colors, decorations and music during the ceremony.

[Q] Which of the following best shows American individualism?

[A] Some people choose their own style of weddings.

(2228) [Q] How is this passage mainly developed?

[A] By giving examples.

→ Answers for MCQs like (2228) could not be rephrased from the text, so such MCQs are not viewed as LLTI, but instead as HLTI or GEN (described in Sections 2.2.4, 2.2.5).

- applying **cause-and-effect reasoning** required for the correct answer relates to the questions which ask for statements to present (potential) reasons and/or results, based on the information given in the text

(3302) [T] The adult may have not intended to hurt me with her words, but it had an after effect. The meeting made me think she had no belief that I could possibly succeed in the future. After that it caused me to try to avoid any future meeting with adults until absolutely necessary.

[Q] *The writer once tried to avoid meetings with adults because _ .*

[A] *he was once hurt by an adult*

(3276) [T] Designed by researchers at Japan's Tsukuba University, the device supports the flex() of the knee, which enables a runner to use 30% less muscle power compared to running unassisted.

[Q] *What is the special feature of the device according to the passage?*

[A] *It helps save physical strength.*

- making **transformations from/to the opposite** means that requested information is derived from negation and converted to assertion, or vice versa, or determines one of the only possible two values

(1360) [T] Chen leads a very simple life. All she needs is food and a place to sleep. Everything else is a luxury .

[Q] *In Chen's eyes, a luxury is about _ .*

[A] everything except food and a bed

(1328) [T] In Arab countries, it is impolite when you eat with your left hand, so don't do it!

[A] In Arab countries you should eat with your right hand.

- **comparing/contrasting** two or more items from the text represents questions that directly or indirectly ask for similarities or differences between two objects/phenomena/events/places etc. described in the text

(1745) [T] Trucking all the heavy glass bottles causes a much larger carbon footprint than the transportation of much lighter boxed wine.

[Q] Compared with glass bottled wine, boxed wine _ .

[A] causes less eco-footprint

(852) [T] A microblog differs from a traditional blog in that its content is typically much smaller, in both actual size and aggregate file size.

[Q] Why is a microblog different from a traditional blog?

[A] Because a microblog has smaller contents than a traditional blog in actual and total file size.

- finding **contrast within alternatives** defines a strategy of inferencing for cases when a correct answer has no direct support in the text but should/can be inferred by excluding other alternatives (see Figure 5).

Text:

At one time silk was reserved only for the Chinese emperor. Gradually, others began wearing silk. In addition to being used for clothing, silk came to have industrial uses in ancient China, something that happened in the West only in modern times. Silk was used to make musical instruments, fishing lines, weapons, ropes and even paper. During the Han Dynasty silk became a form of money. Farmers paid taxes in both rice and silk. The prices of goods were calculated in lengths of silk just as they had once been calculated in gold. The importance of silk is even reflected in the Chinese language. For example, of the 5000 most common Chinese characters, around 500 have silk as their “key”.

Question:

(2796) Which of the following uses of silk is NOT mentioned in the passage?

(A) A way of purchasing goods people sold.

“The prices of goods were calculated in lengths of silk just as they had once been calculated in gold.”

(B) A material used for making different products.

“In addition to being used for clothing, silk came to have industrial uses in ancient China, something that happened in the West only in modern times. Silk was used to make musical instruments, fishing lines, weapons, ropes and even paper.”

(C) A method of paying money to the government.

“Farmers paid taxes in both rice and silk.”

(D) A valuable gift given to foreigners travelling in China.

no direct statement in the text, but this one is the only alternative which has no support from the text

= LLTI by contrast within alternatives

Figure 5: LLTI by contrast within alternatives

2.2.4 High-level text-based inference (HLTI)

- **information outside from the text**, like **prior knowledge from various field(s)** if these cannot be inferred from the passage (e.g., linguistics/literature – to distinguish between the genres of writing; geography – to relate names of countries to corresponding nations: *the USA - American, the Netherlands - Dutch*; mathematics – to derive meaning of the terminology: e.g., *equivalent, difference*, etc.)

- **skills other than reading** (e.g., to calculate)

(1852) [T] *The cost for the cruise, pasta buffet, live music, and the 2.5-hour cruise to Emerald Bay is \$55 (normally \$75). The cost for children between 3-11 is \$41.*

[Q] *How much will Mrs. Robert and her 15-year-old son pay for the cruise?*

- [T] *Our Book-of-the-Month Club will feature 12 books each year. As a member, you will be able to select one new book each month. The membership fee is only \$10.00 per month.*
- (545) [Q] *As a member of the Book-of-the-Month Club, you . . .*
 [A] *need to pay 120 dollars every year*

- **application of the knowledge** gained from reading of a given text **to solve a hypothetical problem not mentioned in the passage**

- [T] *Beijing, China*
Beijing is the second largest city in China and serves as the capital. The city is so old, in fact, that almost every building has some sort of cultural or historic features – no matter how small. Getting around the city you’ll find yourself faced with amazing temples , the largest palaces in the world, and many works of art that leave you breathless.
- (1066*) [Q] *If you want to visit the biggest place where ancient emperors lived in the world, you can go to . . .*
 [A] *Beijing*

- **implementation of specific type of content knowledge** (e.g., generate a definition, theme of a passage or its part, or a purpose of the author)

- (3387) [Q] *One of the experiments shows . . .*
 [A] *laws of physics under weightless conditions*
- (3050) [Q] *The first writing tip given is mostly about . . .*
 [A] *how a student should begin an essay*
- (3424) [Q] *The author wrote the article in order to . . .*
 [A] *remember her father*

Note that there can be a basis in the text to infer a theme or a purpose. For these cases, TOM is not viewed as a HLTI but rather as a LM, SM, or LLTI, depending on conditions the inference satisfies.

- [T] *Last week, we published an article about modern marriage.*
- (1620) [Q] *Last week we published an article about . . .*
 [A] *marriage nowadays*
 → T-Q = LM, T-A = SM

- [T] *”I know that failure is a part of science, but I really feel sorry for my students,” science teacher Greg Adragna told the *Houston, Chronicle* .*
- (3445) [Q] *How did teacher Greg Adragna feel about the explosion of the rocket?*
 [A] *Frustrated.*
 → T-Q = LLTI, by inferences within several clauses, pronominal references; T-A = SM

In contrast to LLTI, the text provides no explicit clues as to which pieces of it are particularly relevant for the MCQ. Instead, readers must determine the relevant parts themselves.

2.2.5 Generation of the appropriate interpretive framework (GEN) The category is used when high-level text-based inference is needed *both* for matching the text and the question (T-Q relations) and for matching the text and the answer (T-A relations) (see Figures 6, 7).

Text:

Study Books

Basic Study Manual Hardcover :\$ 37 Future success depends on the ability to learn. Here are the answers to the questions most often asked by parents, teachers, business trainers and by students themselves. Read this book and learn:

What the three barriers to study are and what to do about them. What to do if you get tired of a subject you are studying. Twenty-six simple drills to help you learn how to study easily, rapidly and with full understanding.

Buy and read Basic Study Manual and use it do dramatically improve your ability to study.

Study Skills for Life Hardcover: \$32 L. Ron Hubbard’s study technology for children opens the door to their future success by giving them the ability to study and learn. Fully illustrated (,) for easy comprehension.

Learning How to Learn Hardcover: \$25 The basics of effective study for 8 to 12-year-olds, fully illustrated. Children who read and apply the materials in this book regain their liking for study and their ability to apply this knowledge in life. Get this book for a child you want to see win at his studies!

How to Use a Dictionary Picture Book for Children Hardcover: \$36

In spite of billions of dollars spent on "educational research", children are not taught the most basic skills of learning, even the most basic of these: how to use a dictionary. In fact, a research of educational books for children found no book that told them how to use a dictionary or that one should. Written for children 8 to 12-year-olds, this fully illustrated book will teach your child:

How to find words in a dictionary.

The different ways that words are used.

What the different marks and symbols that are used in a dictionary mean.

How to use a dictionary to correctly pronounce words. It includes a section for parents and teachers showing you how to use this book with children. Buy this book and give it to your children to unlock their education. What’s more, you will just pay 50% for it before May 1, 2014.

Question:

(3408) If you buy the four books on April 30, 2014, you will have to pay - for them.

hypothetical problem (HLTI)

Key

(B) \$ 112

calculation (HLTI)
= **generation of the appropriate interpretive framework**

Figure 6: Generation of the appropriate interpretive framework (GEN)

Text:

In the absence of established facts, the vast collections of found photographs give our minds an opportunity to wander freely. That, above all, is why they are so fascinating.

Question:

(3213) [...] The author's attitude toward found photographs can be described as _ .

implementation of specific type of content knowledge, information outside from the text to interpret "the author's attitude" (HLTI)

Key

(C) optimistic

prior knowledge to interpret "optimistic" (HLTI)

= **generation of the appropriate interpretive framework**

Figure 7: GEN. In the skipped part of the text (marked with "[...]"), there is no basis for a LM or SM, or LLTI for the words "author" or "attitude" between the T and the Q.

2.3 Number of phrases (NPhr)

NPhr reflects complexity of a question by *the number of* included *independent and dependent clauses*, given that each of such clauses would bring an additional condition/trait to control when determining the correct answer [Kirsch et al., 1999]. As far as *detached predicatives*, prefaces, parentheticals [Biber et al., 1999] are characterised by similar nature and state additional criteria to be satisfied in the correct answer, each of the three is counted as a phrase for NPhr (parsed with "/" in the examples below).

(2392) [Q] /It was very funny/ /when Tom danced on a wooden plate/
/held by a person/ /who was eight feet tall/ because _ .

(2031) [Q] /According to the passage/, /if there are 100 Chinese men smokers in the
room/, /as a result/, /the number of cigarettes /they smoke/ is at least _
each day/.

2.4 Number of items (NI)

NI is the number of parts included to the key, such that each part separately could serve as a relevant (but not complete) answer to the stem. For instance, in case "Bob and Jane" is the correct answer, NI is 2.

For MCQ units where the correct answer consists of a combination of other two or three alternatives given to the same MCQ (e.g., *both A and B*, *both A and C*, *all of the above*, etc.), which are referred to as **complex alternatives** in this paper, NI is counted according to the number of independent alternatives included to the correct answer (see Figures 8 and 9).

Question:*(3301) Who are responsible for children's development at school according to the writer?*

Alternatives	Number of items (points)
(A) Students.	one (0)
(B) Teachers.	one (0)
(C) Headmasters.	one (0)
(D) Both students and teachers.	two (1)

Figure 8: Complex alternative (*D*)**Question:***(3208) Children like the seaside so much, because they can . .*

Alternatives	Number of items (points)
(A) swim in the sea	one (0)
(B) play with the sand	one (0)
(C) take a sun bath	one (0)
(D) do all of the above	three (2)

Figure 9: Complex alternative (*D*)**Question:***(3010) .How did people feel when Tom appeared at his own funeral ?*

Alternatives	Number of items (points)
(A) They were surprised and happy.	two (1)
(B) They were <u>surprised</u> and sad	two (1)
(C) They were <u>worried</u> and excited.	two (1)
(D) They were frightened and happy.	two (1)

Figure 10: Alternatives with one repetitive part of clause ("*surprised*")

Note: alternatives can sometimes share same part of a clause which then appears repetitive for two or more given choices. Unless the same repetition is found in all given alternatives, NI for such MCQs is counted including each repetitive element as a separate item (see Figures 10 and 11).

Question:

(1690) *These advertisements are most probably advertisements - .*

Alternatives	Number of items (points)
(A) <u>on the Internet</u> intended for the general public to read	two (1)
(B) <u>in a newspaper</u> intended for large companies to read	two (1)
(C) on the Internet intended for college students to read	two (1)
(D) <u>in a newspaper</u> intended for college students to read	two (1)

Figure 11: Alternatives with two repetitive parts of a clause ("*on the Internet*", "*in a newspaper*")

Otherwise, such element is ignored for NI (ignored clause is underlined in the example below):

- (917) alternatives
- [Q] *How could noise from building sites be alleviated if Brisbane adopted daylight saving?*
- (A) *If daylight saving was adopted, the daytime would be prolonged and the night would become quieter.*
- (B) *If daylight saving was adopted, the working hours during the daytime would be shortened while the night would be extended and thus quieter.*
- (C) *If daylight saving was adopted, the night would be shortened and thus quieter.*
- (D) *If daylight saving was adopted, both the daytime and the night would be shortened and the noise would be reduced.*

2.5 Number of items transparency (NI_t)

The variable indicates if NI in the correct answer is specified for a reader or can be derived from the MCQ unit structure. MCQs with specified number of items are considered easier and score 0 points, while those with this number unspecified score 1 point.

NI_t can be **specified**:

- by direct instructions in the question

(2819) [Q] *The two important factors for Mullaney's successful family business are - .*

(1978) [Q] *When* and *where* was the worst earthquake ever recorded?

- by structure of the alternatives, when all are composed by the same number of items (Figures 12, 13)

NI_t is assessed as **unspecified** if there are no relevant instructions in the question, and at least one of the alternatives differs from the correct answer in NI (Figure 14).

Question:

(2082) Which of the following words can best describe Jeremie Wentworth?

Alternatives	NIt category
(A) Patient and creative.	NI = two
(B) Calm and brave.	NI = two
(C) Careful and clever.	NI = two
(D) Simple and generous.	NI = two
	= specified, two

Figure 12: NIt is specified by the structure of alternatives

Question:

(3492) How long does the Arundel Festival last this year?

Alternatives	NIt category
(A) 10 days	NI = two, determiner+object
(B) One week	NI = two, determiner+object
(C) 16 days	NI = two, determiner+object
(D) One month	NI = two, determiner+object
	= specified, two

Figure 13: NIt is specified by the structure of alternatives

Question:

(1695) Tourists can experience the Polynesian culture mainly through . .

Alternatives	NIt category
(A) the local people's dresses	NI = one
(B) luxury services and places of entertainment	NI = two
(C) songs and dances	NI = two
(D) cuisines	NI = one
	= unspecified

Figure 14: NIt is unspecified

2.6 Number of required paragraphs (NPar)

The variable represents *minimal* number of paragraphs which is enough for a reader to make one or more corresponding match(es) or inference(s) between the text and question or the text and correct answer. For the RACE evaluation, paragraphs required to relate both text to the question and text to the correct answer are counted. NPar scoring scale is fully adopted from the original evaluation model: inferences to be made within one paragraph are considered easier than those to get between two or more paragraphs, so MCQs of the first mentioned case score 0 points, while MCQs of the second mentioned case receive 1 point.

(3490) [T] In the Castle Shop, you will discover a wide and interesting range of gift ideas for everyone. It offers gifts and souvenirs designed to appeal to all tastes and pockets. Foods, china, books, and stationery are all available. Many are sold in this Castle Shop only. [Par.4]
At Arundel Castle we pride ourselves on supporting local suppliers and actively encourage environmentally friendly products. [Par.5]

[Q] When visiting the castle, you can - .

[A] buy eco-friendly products in the Castle Shop

→ Par.4 proves that it is possible to buy some products when visiting the castle; Par.5 ensures that eco-friendly products are available there. Hence, the complete answer requires **two paragraphs** from the text.

2.7 Infer condition (IC)

According to [Kirsch and Mosenthal, 1995, Kirsch et al., 1999], type of relations between the question and the text, namely *compare* (search for similarities) and *contrast* (search for differences), impacts MCQ complexity level. To cover the difference, this type of relation was introduced as an additional condition (IC) to be assessed [Kirsch, 2001]. For the RACE corpus evaluation, a question for comparison in this context is viewed as that requiring to follow information stated in the text, while a stem for contrast refers to an opposite of that stated in the text (e.g., if certain symptoms of a disease are described in the text and the question asks to select what cannot be viewed as a symptom of this illness). Questions for contrast often include negations like *not*, *except*, or prefixes with negative connotation like *dis-*, *un-*, *im-*, *ir-* etc..

(3055) [T] The reason is simple. All the evidence shows that taking girls out of the fields and homes, and putting them behind desks, raises economic productivity, lowers infant and maternal death rates, reduces birth rates, and improves environmental management.

[Q] Which is Not the reason why educating girls reduces poverty?

[A] It creates more children.

→ IC = contrast, since the question includes a negation (“Not”) and the correct answer opposes to what is stated in the text

Note that *compare/contrast conditions* are always analysed from the perspective of what is stated in the text. Thus, if advantages are discussed in the text, and the Q asks to define an advantage, the IC is assessed as “compare” and not “contrast”.

[T] Scanning text is normally a boring process with each page having to be inserted into a scanner, but the team led by Professor Masatoshi Ishikawa uses a high speed camera that takes 500 pictures a second to scan pages as they are turned by workers.

(842)

[Q] According to the passage, the advantage of the new scanning software is that - .

[A] *it can work much more effectively*

→ IC = compare

[T] The main disadvantage of studying abroad is the cost, not just of your course, but also of your food and travel.

(972) [Q] Compared with two other ways, the obvious disadvantage of studying abroad lies in its - .

[A] *high cost*

→ IC = compare

2.8 Plausibility of distractors (POD)

POD relates to the extent to which information in the text shares one or more features with the information requested in the question but does not fully satisfy what has been requested [Kirsch, 2001], and represented the degree of difficulty associated with selecting the correct answer from among a list [Kirsch and Mosenthal, 1995].

To assess the degree of that, the *distance* between each of the distractors and the correct answer (demonstrating if both are in the same paragraph or not) is taken into account. In case, if all distractors appear in a different paragraph(s) from the correct answer, they are assessed then by *type of match* – each by the same principles as T-A relations for TOM; if at least one of the distractors appears in the same paragraph with the correct answer, the *number of such distractors* is taken for evaluation.

Note: for MCQs where the correct answer is based on information from two or more paragraphs, the notion of “(not) the same paragraph as the correct answer” applies to the whole set of required paragraphs.

Surprisingly, it might not always be clear where the boundary between “*no distracting information in the text*” and “*one or more distractors represent plausible inferences based on information outside the text*” lies, as in both cases one does not see a distractor directly in the text. Thus, for RACE evaluation, the following rules are applied:

- if at least one of the distractors “based on information outside the text” can be inferred from any part of the text, meaning there is a phrase, a sentence or a sequence of these which can serve as a basis(es) for such distractor⁴, we assess it as a plausible one, scored the highest (5 points) (see Figure 15);
- if a distractor is “based on information outside the text” but has no reference to the text, meaning that it cannot be literally or synonymously matched to the text and there is no basis for a corresponding inference from the text, such distractor is evaluated as *irrelevant*, meaning “there is no distracting information in the text”, scored the lowest (1 point) (see Figure 16).

⁴ where possible, text references for such distractors are marked in the texts as bases for the alternatives (for details, see section 5.3)

Text:

Thanks to the newly arrived shuttle Endeavour, the space station now has five sleep stations, two baths, two kitchens and two mini-gyms. Altogether, there are nine rooms, three of which are full scale labs.

Question:

(2631) Which of the following is true about Endeavour according to the passage?

Alternatives	Commentaries
(A) Endeavour is a newly built shuttle	distractor ; can be perceived true if “built” is erroneously treated as a synonym to “arrived”
(B) Endeavour is part of the space station	distractor ; can be perceived true if a wrong inference is made about the shuttle becoming a part of the space station after the arrival
(C) Endeavour didn’t get close to the space station	distractor ; no data about the distance is given in the text, though it can be inferred that must have reached close enough to the space station to deliver all the stuff
(D) Endeavour carried a lot of equipment for the space* station	correct answer

Figure 15: Distractors cannot be found in the text, viewed as plausible

Note: since MCQ units are evaluated in terms of their relation to the text, distractors which might be true for reality but cannot be inferred from the given text are also treated as *irrelevant* (see Example 17). The same rules apply to series of common-sense distractors – they might not be (all) mentioned in the text, but one can expect to face them as something natural and generally known (e.g., sequence of numbers – 1, 2, 3, 4 or 40, 50, 60, 70; geographical directions – north, south, east, west; days of the week; months; types of changes – increased, decreased, stayed the same; etc.). For examples, see Figures 18 and 19.

In case if distractors for the same MCQ appear in different assessment categories, the one to score the highest is preferable for evaluation, since this will be the closest to the correct answer, representing the maximum number of conditions/traits to be verified and thus, reflecting the required minimum of knowledge and skills from a reader to detect the correct answer (illustrated by Figure 20).

Text:

Going to school is difficult for more than 13 million children in India. They must go to work instead, or go hungry. That's why India began the Mid-Day Meal Scheme, the largest school-lunch program in the world. A free lunch encourages children to come to school and gives them the energy they need for learning. The program began in the 1960s.

Question:

(2572) *Why is it difficult for children to go to school in India?*

Alternatives	Commentaries
(A) Because there are not enough teachers.	distractor ; no data about number of teachers is given in the text
(B) Because there are not enough schools.	distractor ; no data about number of schools is given in the text
(C) Because they have to work to make money.	correct answer
(D) Because their parents refuse to send them to school.	distractor ; no data about parents' attitude to schools in India is given in the text

Figure 16: Distractors cannot be found in the text, viewed as irrelevant

Text:

Men are more likely to have much less patience than women. That is why their stress levels are much higher than women when they are sitting still in traffic. Men want to get where they are going now.

Question:

(2261) *Why are men under more stress than women when stuck in a traffic jam?*

Alternatives	Commentaries
(A) Because they drive more than women.	distractor ; might appear true to life but the text says nothing about it
(B) Because they are less patient than women.	correct answer
(C) Because they face more stress than women at work.	distractor ; same as for (A)
(D) Because they are less clear about where to go than women.	distractor ; same as for (A)

Figure 17: Distractors cannot be found in the text (though might be true for reality), viewed as irrelevant

Text:

Kenneth worked as a railroad car inspector and mechanic before becoming a mail carrier for the Post Office. He was active in the church as a Sunday teacher.

Question:

(3347) *How many jobs did Kenneth get?*

Alternatives	Commentaries
(A) Four.	correct answer
(B) Three.	distractor ; can be perceived as correct if a piece of information is missed when counting
(C) Two.	distractor ; same as for (B)
(D) One.	distractor ; same as for (B)

Figure 18: Common-sense distractors with potential inferences from the text, viewed as plausible

Text:

Kabul, Oct. 28 (Xinhuanet)— Unknown armed men in military uniform kidnapped three staff of the United Nations in the Afghan capital city at broad daylight Thursday, Afghan officials confirmed .

Question:

(1090) *When did this kidnapping take place?*

Alternatives	Commentaries
(A) At night	distractor ; no basis in the text to make such inference, irrelevant
(B) In the daytime	correct answer
(C) Early in the morning	distractor ; same as for (A)
(D) at dawn	distractor ; same as for (A)

Figure 19: Common-sense distractors with no inference from the text, viewed as irrelevant

Text:

*Then about sixty years ago, supermarkets were born. In a supermarket, people could get all the different kinds of food they needed without going to different stores. [Par.2]

The recent change in American shopping was the superstore. Large chain stores such as Wal-Mart, Office Depot and Toys “R” Us have been built all across the United States. Because they are so large, they can buy goods at a great discount and sell them much cheaper than smaller stores. [Par.4]

Sometimes, when they are built near small towns, many of the small town stores have to close. They just cannot compete with their giant neighbors. [Par.5]

Question:

(2661) *Why can the superstores sell products at much lower prices?*

Alternatives	Points	Commentaries
(A) Because they are built near small towns.	1.5	distractor ; LM, <u>not</u> the same paragraph as the correct answer [Par.5]
(B) Because they are across the United States.	4	distractor ; LM, the same paragraph as the correct answer [Par.4]
(C) Because they sell all kinds of products people need.	3	distractor ; LLTI, <u>not</u> the same paragraph as the correct answer [Par.2]
(D) Because they can buy goods at a reduction in the price.	n/a	<u>correct answer</u> [Par.4]

Figure 20: Distractors belonging to different categories of POD

2.9 Type of calculation (TOC)

TOC was initially elaborated by [Kirsch et al., 1999] as an additional variable for quantitative literacy evaluation, mainly necessary for comprehension of noncontinuous texts or documents. The variable represented types of arithmetic operation (*addition, subtraction, multiplication, or division*) and whether that operation must be performed alone or in combination. TOC is included as a process variable to the evaluation model for RACE, with no alterations to the original scale. This allows to detect (and distinguish in complexity degree) tasks which certainly require specific prior knowledge and/or skills apart from reading (namely, performing mathematical operations) from the tasks based exclusively on RC skills.

However, one-by-one counting, which appears in approximately 20% of all calculation-related MCQs of the evaluated RACE materials (questions like “*How many characters are mentioned in this story?*”(262), “*How many people does Mr. Brown see in the street one day? He sees _ in all.*”(3425)) was not initially discussed among the types of operation. As a solution for the RACE corpus evaluation, if no other operation(s) required, such MCQs get the same scoring as for *single addition* (which is treated as the easiest), since this type of calculation itself is basic for all other mathematical operations.

3 Glossary of errors (with examples)

Additional notes – an MCQ element contains special characters, symbols, or remarks (e.g., *prefix = st1 /, s6t—*, etc.) which are not related to the main content, are unnecessary for a reader in the context of a reading comprehension test (e.g., *number of words, source references*, etc.), or provide vague specifications.

Note: explanations of the vocabulary in the texts and/or synonyms used to clarify meaning of a word/phrase are not counted as A.n..

Ambiguously formulated – the question is formulated in a way that does not make the query clear or allows two possible interpretations of the question:

- (1630) alternatives [Q] *What is the disadvantage of a credit card?*
(A) *The bank charges annual fees for credit cards.*
(B) *The interest rate for credit cards is rather high.*
(C) *Credit cards cause argument among holders and banks.*
(D) *Credit cards tend to lead card holder into debt*

Explanation: the text, as well as the alternatives, mentions both banks (“credit card companies”) and credit card holders, so it stays unclear the disadvantage for whom is expected as the correct answer, given that the alternatives can be interpreted as (dis)advantages for both of the two sides mentioned.

Sometimes, the error can be a result of wrongly used pronouns in the question (e.g., *An old friend of mine called . . .* (3335)).

Answerable without reading – it is possible to answer the question by analysing alternatives, without reading the given passage, or even without reading the alternatives (often applies to questions which imply stable facts, common truth, meanings of expressions, and definitions).

Extra gaps – a piece of information is or might be missed in an MCQ element, though has no significant influence on general understanding of the content and answering the given question (if the E.g. is in the text, it might appear misleading for another question to the same text). Some of the gaps are marked with an underscore (.).

Extra spaces (punctuation) – one or more spaces are inserted before/after a punctuation mark where they considered erroneous according to the English language rules.

Extra spaces (within a word or a digit) – one or more spaces are inserted in the middle of a word or a multi-digit number, which leads to a (misleading) spelling error or confusion in the data interpretation: *And if the attack of hard times should fall upon their weft-heeled member ship?*

Here, web addresses are counted as one word, currency symbol and figure are counted as one digit; stable phrases and abbreviations with no fixed written form (e.g., *a.m. / am / AM*, etc.) are only checked for consistent formatting within the text.

Formatting inconsistency – for texts, means that formatting rules for abbreviations, numbers, or lists are not completely followed (similarly to the way the definition applies for alternatives);

for questions, means that the part claimed to be formatted in a certain way (e.g., underlined) cannot be found as such or differs in actual formatting;

for alternatives, formatting rules (e.g., capitalisation of the first word, punctuation in the end of an alternative, etc.) differ within one and the same MCQ unit.

The issue is treated as problematic as it might be used as a meta-clue for a correct answer (especially, when only one of the alternatives differ in formatting from the other) or cause certain confusion for a reader when interpreting the information given in the passage.

Grammatical errors – a sentence contains a faulty, uncommon, or controversial usage of the English language (e.g., pronoun disagreement, misuse of articles, grammar tenses, modifiers, etc.), or breaks the English grammar rules.

Incomplete alternative(s) – one or more of the alternatives fails to provide a comprehensible piece of information to be related to the given question and/or text.

Incomplete question – the question fails to provide a comprehensible query and/or cannot be related to the text.

Incomplete text – the text does not provide enough information to relate the question.

Inconsistency between A – alternatives within one and the same MCQ unit do not correspond in represented type of content.

Inconsistency between Q and A – question and one or more of the alternatives within one and the same MCQ unit represent different types of information.

Inconsistency between T and A – the data provided in the text do not correspond semantically to that in one or more of the alternatives.

Inconsistency between T and Q – the data requested by the question is not provided or cannot be inferred from the text.

Misleading gap(s) – a piece of information is missed in an MCQ element and prevents a reader from understanding of the content and/or answering the given question (if a M.g. is in the text, it often appears in the area identified as a required paragraph and/or a basis for one or more of the alternatives). The gaps might or might not be marked with an underscore (_):

This practice is common in some countries, like the United Kingdom, where it's called a “ _ ”.

The ceremony and reception were _ They were attended by many rich and famous people and by about two thousand guests.

Before he worked in an insurance company, what was Mr. Briggs? _

The robot dog Biscuit is less likely to /M.g., not marked/ the disorder of your house and except for a few dead batteries, won't leave any surprises on the floor.

Misleading spaces – one or more spaces are inserted before/after a punctuation mark where they are considered erroneous according to the English language rules, and lead to (misleading) spelling errors.

Misleading spelling errors – a word/phrase is formed incorrectly in terms of choice of letters, order of letters, or usage of special characters/symbols (e.g., hyphens, apostrophes), which makes it impossible to recognise the affected word/phrase properly or results in a different word/phrase implying other meaning(s):

The communication between subterranean and above-ground insects has only been studied in a few systems.

By 2013, only 50% of 1995 levels of waste will benllewed to be sent to landfill.

Which of the following can be the best tide of the passage?

(A) he doesn't give thim any vegetables or fruit

Missing spaces (between words and/or digits) – lack of a blank area to separate two or more words or a word and a digit (e.g., *By 2013, only 50% of 1995 levels of waste will benllewed to be sent to landfill.*; *The study looked at 50 1,2 and 3 year olds.*; *The Tianqiao area of Beijing won its name as the city's major outdoor performance site*);

can also lead to (misleading) spelling errors: *Women who cannot afford to throw away clothing in this way, waste hours of their time altering the dresses they have. Skirts are lengthened or shortened; neck-lines are lowered or raised, and soon.*

Missing spaces (punctuation) – lack of a blank area to separate one or more punctuation marks from a following word, digit, or another punctuation mark, according to the English language punctuation rules.

OCR errors – faults caused by inaccurate optical character recognition process; often leads to (misleading) spelling errors (e.g., *(B) cscapre predaton*), digits inserted in a word (e.g., *[...]submit just one more scholarship application when 180 0thers had already turned me down;* *He admitted his private custoIlll I'8 have fallen off a bit*), and letters inserted in a multi-digit number (e.g., *turns 10 years old*).

Overlapping alternatives – more than one alternative satisfy the conditions stated in the question and thus result in more than one correct answer to one and the same question.

Punctuation errors – wrong choice or usage of punctuation symbols, according to the English language punctuation rules (e.g., periods used instead of commas and vice versa, unnecessary or missed punctuation marks in a sentence).

Spelling errors (except hyphens and contractions) – a word/phrase is formed incorrectly in terms of choice of letters, order of letters, capitalisation or usage of special symbols according to the rules of British or American English, depending on the language of a particular text.

Spelling errors (hyphens, contractions) – incorrect usage of hyphens and contractions (or missing symbols) which is often a result of extra or missing spaces and might lead to misleading spelling errors (e.g., *Why do people cross their fingers when facing difficulties-eve non-religious people?; Skin - diving is a new sport today.; Along with him, I will send you what he likes and dislikes, his favorite things to do and his personal self portrait.; Zoe 's success became a news item.; When my guys heard that this opportunity was here, they said, 'Let' s do it for free. We got to get it.No one else can do it. '; Rival models include Tesco Metro and Sainsburys Local.).*

Subjective formulation – the question or one or more of the alternatives requires evaluation of an object or phenomenon basing on a reader's personal opinion, feelings or experience, where the answer will likely lack grounds for support or declination, and consequently, for objective evaluation:

What's the best title for the text?

What do you think of the carpenter? (2789)

What is probably the most effective way to control alcohol? (2501)

In which hotels can guests book a trip more conveniently? (1522)

The author said that they depended on each other in the same way because .. (B) they both drove their car at a terrific speed (2686)

Syntax errors – incorrect word order in one or more sentences, or unnecessary repetition of one or more syntactic unit (e.g., *But nowadays, a wife has to help her husband earn the bread and butter as well as well as looking after her family.*).

Time-dependent – the requested information is related to the period of time that passed from the date of publication of the text or from when an event discussed in the passage happened till the text has been published; this makes the correct answer not stable and requires changes in corresponding periods of time (e.g., months, years, etc.).

How old may Miss Lund be now? (1812)

(A) During the last half year, our economy has grown fastest since 2003. (3318)

(A) It has a history of over 30 years. (1349)

[T] *"That's the one that made it, the letter to the paper a few months ago," he said. "It's like a dream come true. The last time we ever heard from Margery was in 1953 after the floods. She wrote home to know if we were all right. My sister Dorothy wrote back, But Margery had moved again and never got the letter." [...]*

(3112) *Now 88, she was recovering after several months in hospital, but immediately recognized her brother.*

[Q] *When she wrote to John last time ,Margery was -*

[A] *34 years old*

→ it is impossible to count the age without a reference to the date the word "now" implies; the date of publication is unknown from the given text.

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